

Unity in Diversity through Education: Revisiting Sri Aurobindo in the Era of NEP 2020

Shalu Devi

Department of Education (CIE)

University of Delhi, Delhi, India, Email: shaluyadav242@gmail.com

Received : 22/02/2026

1st BPR : 29/02/2026

2nd BPR : 08/03/2026

Accepted : 16/03/2026

Abstract

Sri Aurobindo visualizes human unity not merely as a product of economic and political arrangement but also as a profound spiritual evolution of consciousness. In his original writings, he explored the historical, psychological and spiritual forces that drive humanity towards collective integration of mankind. Unity here doesn't simply mean uniformity but he himself celebrates the harmonious diversity rooted in spiritual awakening. According to him humanity develops from clan and tribe to nation state, and ultimately towards a global unity grounded in shared consciousness. We as humans respect this notion of shared consciousness to progress further in any area. This true human unity and notion of shared consciousness would be achieved through spiritual realization and not by coercion or homogenization.

On one side, where we witness cultural fragmentation, interconnectedness, environmental crises, political conflicts and geopolitical tensions, his thoughts gave us an alternative paradigm that reiterates the importance of global solidarity, spiritual humanism and shared consciousness. His educational philosophy also gave a transformative vision of integral development of students. Based on some of his epic works like *The Human Cycle* and *The Life Divine* one can elicit that in his educational philosophy also he puts consciousness, self-development and unity in diversity as prime ideas.

This paper tries to present the educational philosophy of Aurobindo in light of National Education Policy 2020. Sri Aurobindo's thoughts are profoundly relevant for modern schooling because they integrate spiritual insights with current educational practices in our education system. His vision on education gave a paradigmatic shift from rote memorisation to conscious awakening of soul. NEP 2020 reiterates the slogan of holistic development which is one of the important aspects of Aurobindo's philosophy. This paper gave a comprehensive understanding on implementing Aurobindo's philosophy in schools to bring a sustainable change in the present education system.

Keywords: Educational Philosophy, Consciousness, Interconnectedness, Sustainable Change.

1. Introduction:

Education is the basic force which transforms an individual into the most constructive and productive resource. Philosophy gives you a depth in thoughts and decision making too. Education and philosophy are two important components to the overall development of an individual. India, like all other countries, witnesses diverse educational philosophies because of historic transformations of societies, influx of heterogenous ideas absorbed from various communities who colonised India.

Sri Aurobindo (1872-1950) visualizes human unity not merely as a product of economic and political arrangement but also as a profound spiritual evolution of consciousness. In his original writings, he explored the historical, psychological and spiritual forces that drive humanity towards collective integration of mankind.

He was one of the most eminent philosophers, yogis and educationists of his time. As a philosopher, his ideas integrate Indian historical and spiritual traditions with modern views. In some of his seminal

works like *The life divine*, *The synthesis of yoga* and *The Human Cycle* he shared his ideas on transformation of inner self and conscience, unity in diversity and spiritual evolution of self. He gave a concept of divine consciousness which evolved the universe. This evolution is not only biological and physical but also psychological as mentioned in *The life divine*. His theories are an amalgamation of eastern spirituality and western rational inquiry, which emphasizes the harmony of spirit and matter.

As a yogi, he gave a concept of 'Integral Yoga' which emphasised on transformation of complete self rather than focusing only on renunciation. His yogic journey can transform the human and realize the divine consciousness within. Rather than attaining personal liberation only, he wrote that one should focus on the spiritual evolution of humanity. A balanced personality is a complete and empowered personality according to his concept of integral yoga.

In this article, we would like to discuss his contribution towards education as an educationist. He gave the idea of 'Integral education' which focuses on the overall development of self. This holistic development of individuals includes physical, vital, mental, psychic and spiritual domains. In his seminal writings he discussed that the aim of education should be focused upon developing the inner faculties and potentialities of the child. Child centered teaching and learning interventions are prime domains of his educational philosophies.

In a rapidly changing world, his ideas are apt for imbibing value based and need based education. Education should not be limited to acquisition of knowledge and skills but also aims to develop the intellectual, emotional, social, moral and spiritual human personality. Character formation by instilling values like empathy, discipline, integrity and cooperation is also equally important. National Education Policy 2020 also reiterates the same slogan of developing a holistic self. He admires the fact that the chief aim of education should be to help the growing soul to draw out what is best and make it perfect for a noble use (Aurobindo,2003, p.12). This idea resonates well with the idea of holistic development of learners as mentioned in NEP 2020. His concept of integral education is also aligned with the multidisciplinary and holistic education which aims to develop cognitive, social, ethical, and emotional skills. He once said, "Nothing can be taught.

The teacher is not an instructor or taskmaster; he is a helper and a guide". These progressive ideas are very much relevant and applicable in the current scenario. NEP 2020 also emphasised on learner-centered pedagogy, experiential learning, critical thinking and role of teacher as a facilitator which reflects Aurobindo's educational philosophy efficiently.

The rationale behind this study is to understand the relevance of Aurobindo's educational philosophy in the context of contemporary educational reforms, particularly the recent National policy on education 2020. With the views of Aurobindo, we also wanted to discover the role of a teacher in developing the self-consciousness of a learner. In light of Aurobindo's seminal works, this study also tries to suggest ways of integrating Aurobindo's philosophy into contemporary educational practices. Therefore, the present study focuses on analyzing the key concepts of Sri Aurobindo's educational philosophy and examines the linkages corresponding with the principles and objectives of NEP 2020 to promote a more balanced, humane and value based education system. The research attempts to demonstrate the potential of integrating traditional philosophical insights with progressive and modern educational reforms (particularly with NEP 2020).

2. Objectives:

1. To explore the relevance of Aurobindo's educational philosophy in the context of NEP 2020.
2. To examine the role of a teacher in developing the self-consciousness of a learner with the help of Aurobindo's philosophy.
3. To suggest ways of integrating Aurobindo's philosophy into contemporary educational practices.

3. Methodology:

This qualitative research lies in the interpretative paradigm. Philosophical analysis was done to elicit the required data. The original writings of Sri Aurobindo and Policy document of NEP 2020 were used as prime sources for analysis.

4. Educational philosophy of Sri Aurobindo in context of NEP 2020:

The educational philosophy of Sri Aurobindo lies in a humanistic approach. His original ideas on spiritual development, integral education, child centred learning and value based education system act as strong pillars to contemporary educational reforms. Many of his ideas are the prime base for provisions and recommendations given in NEP 2020. Major features of NEP 2020 in alignment of Sri Aurobindo's educational philosophy are as follows:

- Holistic and Multidisciplinary education
- Experiential Learning
- Self-realization of inner self
- Child centered learning
- Development of critical thinking and creativity
- Values and moral based education
- Flexibility in curriculum
- Focus on character building and ethics

Following are some of the examples which reiterates and affirms this kind of linkages between traditional philosophical insights and modern educational reforms.

4.1. Integral Education (Holistic Development) for an individual:

Among his famous ideas, Integral education is one which deals with the overall development of human personality. According to Sri Aurobindo, education should not only focus upon intellectual aspects but on all five aspects of human nature namely- Physical, Vital, Mental, Psychic and Spiritual.

As he clearly stated, "Education to be complete must have five principal aspects relating to five principal activities of the humans: The physical, the vital, the mental, the psychic and the spiritual." (Aurobindo, 2008, p.15).

In parallel, NEP 2020 also reiterates the importance of holistic development and transforming the school and higher education institution curriculum in such a manner that they reflect elements from intellectual, physical, emotional and ethical domains. This policy also promotes multidisciplinary learning and overall personality development over mere mental development.

4.2. Self-realization of inner development:

According to Aurobindo's educational philosophy, the ultimate aim of education should be self-discovery and self-actualisation. One should discover the inner potentialities and capabilities during an educational journey.

"The chief aim of education should be to help the growing soul to draw out that which is best and make it perfect for a noble use". (Aurobindo, 2003, p.12)

Education therefore is a means of inner awakening of the soul rather than mere accumulation of facts and information.

4.3. Child-Centered education:

Sri Aurobindo strongly believes in child centric teaching and learning processes. Every child is unique in different ways, one should respect and cater to their uniqueness. The education system should understand the interests, nature and pace of the learner first and then needs to make provisions accordingly.

He once said, "Nothing can be taught. The teacher is not an instructor and taskmaster. Rather, he is a guide and a facilitator.

If we look deeper into recommendations and provisions mentioned in NEP 2020, then we appreciate the fact that NEP also promotes child centric approach in education by promoting experiential learning, critical thinking, inquiry based learning and competency based education.

4.4. Flexibility in Educational Choices:

According to Sri Aurobindo education should be free from any boundaries which restricts the inner self of a learner. Absolute freedom is required for true learning. Education should provide them the platform to appreciate and explore their hidden potentials and capacities. Education should nurture creative and independent thinking rather than mere memorization.

National Education Policy 2020, emphasises flexibility in curriculum, choice of subjects, innovation and creativity in a multidisciplinary education system.

4.5. Moral and Spiritual Education:

When we go deeper into his writings then we understand that he emphasized a lot on achieving two major goals that are ethical values and spiritual awareness. Education is a path to achieve these goals. He believes that humanity is evolving to a higher spiritual consciousness and therefore to nurture universal values of compassion, cooperation and unity is important.

"The destiny of the human race is to move towards a greater unity and harmony" (Aurobindo,2005,p.35). NEP 2020 on the same grounds promotes value based education, concept of empathy and global citizenship.

5. Role of a teacher in developing the self-consciousness of a learner:

The teacher is a very important stakeholder in the teaching learning process. It is the key actor in implementing the provisions and recommendations of any educational reforms or policy document.

5.1. Developing self conscience and inner potentialities :

In Aurobindo's educational philosophy teachers play a pivotal role in nurturing the self conscience and inner potentialities of the learner. According to Sri Aurobindo, education is not only memorising certain facts and figures but actual education is the complete transformation of the learner into a more actualised and spiritual self. Therefore, in light of Aurobindo's philosophy a teacher is not merely a storehouse of information but a guide and facilitator who supports the learner's journey towards self- awareness and spiritual growth. The true duty of a teacher is to encourage independent thinking and self-discovery.

As we know, every child is born with unique innate abilities and as a teacher our role is to create an environment that allows these inner potentials to unfold naturally. By encouraging self expression, teachers support their learners to become aware of their conscious self. From his seminal writings one can draw that self-consciousness is linked closely with psychic and spiritual growth. Therefore, through balanced guidance and value oriented teaching teachers can develop a balanced personality and ethical awareness in their respective learners.

5.2. Encouraging freedom and individual growth:

A good teacher will always encourage democratic environment in their classrooms, providing complete freedom to learners so they can nurture their potential and capabilities. Teachers always give a pool of opportunities to his/her learners to explore and discover their true inner self. An ideal teacher allows the learners to develop their social, cognitive, physical and moral self altogether. They believe and respect unity in diversity which is the root of the Indian knowledge system. By identifying their learner's areas of interest, they provide personalized guidance. A good teacher will always discover the true talent of their learners, like some students are good in maths, some excel in science, some are excellent in co-curricular activities and then they encourage them to pursue their strengths rather than compelling them to follow uniformity.

As per NEP 2020, learners can choose subjects of their own choice which is a part of their flexible curricula and multidisciplinary learning. Teachers can help their learners to map their subject choices without manipulating their student's original interests. This will also help in developing decision making, critical thinking and solving real life problems.

The Key objective of SDG (Sustainable Development Goal) 4 is to ensure inclusive and equitable quality educational opportunities and promote life long learning for all. This can also be achieved by teachers efficiently. As they are the actual implementers of any reform, educational policy, provision or norm at grassroot level. So, a teacher can mentor and facilitate their students not only academically but holistically. Teachers by helping them can develop self-awareness, moral and spiritual values and ethical responsibility.

5.3. Teacher as a role model:

Teachers' role extends far beyond classroom instruction. By fostering freedom, reflection, inner awareness, spirituality and self-consciousness, teachers help learners realize their true potential and develop into balanced individuals capable of contributing positively to society.

Students used to follow their teachers passionately. Teachers who demonstrate integrity, spiritual awareness and wisdom inspire learners to cultivate similar qualities within themselves. Thus, the teacher's personality and conduct shapes the learner's personality and inner development. Aurobindo(1956) envisioned the role of teacher in learners' life as a facilitator of integral education and helped them in developing their multiple facets. The aim of the teacher should also be to educate the child for upcoming challenges in real life with maturity, sensitivity and patience. Teachers serve as an inspiration and mentor who helped the learner to discover their true potential and purpose of life. The teacher also acts as a cultivator of consciousness and achieves self actualisation which is the ultimate goal of life.

6. Suggestions/ Recommendations for integrating Aurobindo's philosophy into contemporary educational practices:

Sri Aurobindo's educational philosophy aligns well with modern educational reforms like NEP 2020 and NCFSE 2023 etc. the primary concept of his educational philosophy is integral education which aims at complete development of physical, mental, psychic, emotional and spiritual. Here spiritual does not mean religious. It has a deep meaning and spirituality in Aurobindo's philosophy is to discover the inner self and connect with the supreme almighty.

6.1. Holistic curriculum to acquire integral education:

Integrate scholastic and non-scholastic domains in the curriculum which provide opportunities to create a balanced being. Integrate yoga, meditation, sports, arts with maths, science, hindi, social-studies and english. Encouraging students to discover their creative self via theatre, crafts, music etc. an element of community engagement and social service should also be present in the school curriculum which develops a sense of empathy and fraternity among students.

6.2. Child- centered and flexible learning:

Sri Aurobindo expresses that nothing can be taught, teachers can only help or guide the learner rest they do by themselves. Allow students to become the navigator and pathfinders of their own journey, teachers will act as a facilitator only. Encourage project based learning, experiential learning, self-directed learning, activity based learning etc which develops a sense of autonomy in the learners. So they become the path finders rather than just the followers.

6.3. Role of teacher as a guide and facilitator:

The role of a teacher is to act as a facilitator and guide not as a dictator of knowledge. A good teacher will always discover the true interest and potential of their learner rather than imposing their own ideas and authority. Teachers can promote open and fair debates, discussions, reflections etc to develop the critical thinking within their students.

6.4. Integration of spiritual and Ethical Education:

The main aim of education should be to discover inner consciousness, spiritual and ethical education. Teachers are the role models for learners so both (teachers and the learners) should engage in community enrichment plans and return positive values to the society. Teachers can create a space within their classrooms for self-reflection and dialogue on ethical issues.

6.5. Educate the learners for human unity and global citizenship:

Sri Aurobindo delivers the concepts of human unity in diversity and harmony among the people. We can even implement his progressive ideas in today's context by encouraging peace education, intercultural understanding and global citizenship.

Finally, we conclude by saying that by integrating the ideas of Sri Aurobindo into contemporary educational practices can transform education into a more complete and holistic process. By emphasizing on developing and nurturing the inner self, by providing freedom of learning , creativity and moral growth, the education system can transform learners into change agents.

7. Implications for contemporary education:

Sri Aurobindo's ideas and educational philosophy are even relevant today. He believed that education should always cater to five aspects in an individual's personality- physical, vital (emotional), mental, psychic and spiritual. So modern education should go beyond the competitive exam based system and promote physical fitness, emotional intelligence, moral values and spiritual consciousness along with intellectual development.

Providing child centered education, freedom in teaching learning processes, developing critical thinking, providing moral and spiritual education, adapting inquiry based approach in problem solving are some of the key implications of his educational theory in the Indian education system. Education should not be for individual's development but for human unity and development of mankind. He envisioned education as a means of promoting fraternity, peace, harmony and universal tranquility. Exam oriented education would destroy the innate ability of learners to explore and learn. Modern education should promote innovation, creativity and a life long learning attitude among learners.

8. Challenges in implementation of his educational philosophy:

Modern education is mostly marks and competition based. This notion corrupts the true potential of a learner to explore and learn at his/her own pace. To perform better in exams learners start memorising the concepts rather than understanding them deeply. This creates a great vacuum in their cognitive domain. However, Aurobindo's approach is to focus on self-exploration, creativity and inner growth which is difficult to measure through traditional examinations.

Rigid curriculum, time bound syllabus, lack of teacher preparedness, large class sizes, limited awareness of Indian educational philosophies, institutional resistance to pedagogical change, little focus on spiritual and moral education are some of the other challenges in this domain.

9. Conclusion

Sri Aurobindo's contribution as a philosopher, yogi and educationist presents a sole purpose and aim of human development. His philosophy gave stages of psychological human evolution, his yoga provides the means of achieving that path of inner transformation and his educational ideas provide the holistic development of human beings. This profound combination of all three will provide a holistic framework for understanding human capabilities and potentialities to build a harmonious society. Integrating his ideas can create balanced, ethical, and creative individuals.

Such integration can strengthen India's education system in the 21st century.

Bibliography:

- Aurobindo, S. (1997). *The life divine*. Sri Aurobindo Ashram Press.
- Aurobindo, S. (1999). *The synthesis of Yoga*. Sri Aurobindo Ashram Press.
- Aurobindo, S. (2003). *A system of national education*. Sri Aurobindo Ashram Press.
- Aurobindo, S. (1999). *The human cycle*. Sri Aurobindo Ashram Press.
- Aurobindo, S. (2003). *The foundations of Indian culture*. Sri Aurobindo Ashram Press.
- Chaudhuri, H., & Spiegelberg, F. (Eds.). (1970). *The integral philosophy of Sri Aurobindo: A commemorative symposium*. George Allen & Unwin.
- Iyengar, K. R. S. (2001). *Sri Aurobindo: A biography and a history*. Sri Aurobindo International Centre of Education.
- Mishra, M. (2017). Integral education and its relevance in modern educational practices. *International Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 7(2), 321-327.
- Sharma, R. A. (2018). Educational philosophy of Sri Aurobindo and its relevance in contemporary education. *International Journal of Advanced Educational Research*, 3(2), 45-49.

Reports and Policy Documents:

- National Education Policy 2020
- Ministry of Education, Government of India. (2020). *National education policy 2020*. Government of India.
- Sustainable Development Goal 4
- United Nations. (2015). *Transforming our world: The 2030 agenda for sustainable development*. United Nations.

